

Catalytic Proton Dynamics at the Water/solid Interface of Ceria-supported Pt Clusters

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Supporting Information Placeholder

ABSTRACT: Wet conditions in heterogeneous catalysis can substantially improve the rate of surface reactions by assisting the diffusion of reaction intermediates between surface reaction sites. The atomistic mechanisms underpinning this accelerated mass transfer are however concealed by the complexity of the dynamic water/solid interface. Here we employ *ab initio* molecular dynamics simulations to disclose the fast diffusion of protons and hydroxide species along the interface between water and ceria, a catalytically important highly-reducible oxide. Up to 20% of the interfacial water molecules are shown to dissociate at room temperature via proton transfer to surface O atoms, leading to partial surface hydroxylation and to a local increase of hydroxide species in the surface solvation layer. A water-mediated Grotthus-like mechanism is shown to activate the fast and long-range proton diffusion at the water/oxide interface. We demonstrate the catalytic importance of this dynamic process for water dissociation at ceria-supported Pt nanoparticles, where the solvent accelerates the spillover of ad-species between oxide and metal sites.

INTRODUCTION

Chemical reactions at the interface between water and solid surfaces underpin diverse fundamental biological processes and valuable technological applications including biomineralization, corrosion, photochemical water splitting, wet heterogeneous catalysis, and fuel-cell electrochemistry, to cite just a few. Water is in fact regularly present in ambient reaction conditions. Moreover, water-based approaches to heterogeneous catalysis in industrial

chemistry are cheap and sustainable alternatives to expensive and toxic solvents [1]. In all these cases, the structure and dynamics of the first water layers in contact with the solid surface profoundly impact on heterogeneous catalysis: The effects of moisture at the active sites range from increasing the catalytic activity by orders of magnitudes, as for CO oxidation on oxide-supported Au nanoparticles [2], to catalyst deactivation, as for methane combustion on metal-oxide catalysts [3]. These effects, resulting from the presence of interfacial water, have been shown to originate from a combination of various factors: the altered reaction mechanisms/thermodynamics and electron energy levels due to solvation [4], the site-competition between water and reactants/intermediates [5], or the modified mass transport between active sites [6]. Partially dissociated water molecules at the liquid/solid interface can mediate and accelerate the diffusion of H atoms on FeO films [6,7,8], and can increase the proton-transfer rate on ZnO, GaN and TiO₂ photocatalytic surfaces [9, 10, 11]. Solvent polarization effects were shown to affect the charge state of catalytic oxide-supported metal nanoparticles, to create new active sites [12], or to affect the electron-level alignment at photocatalytic mixed-oxide photoanodes [13]. These and similar works evidenced the important and elusive effects of interfacial water molecules in wet heterogeneous catalysis and opened the question on how to control and exploit the solvent effects in catalyst design.

We show here that surface wetting strongly affects the equilibrium of water dissociation and leads to a local increase of H⁺ and OH⁻ species at an important water/oxide catalytic interface. The increased local acidity triggers a fast Grotthus-like diffusion mechanism, which is

confined in the interface region and which allows for transferring the species along the interface over several lattice sites and with diffusion rates $\sim 10^{12} \text{ s}^{-1}$. We demonstrate the catalytic importance of this effect for oxide-supported Pt nanoparticles, where this diffusion mechanism couples the water dissociation at the oxide surface sites with the transport and adsorption of adspecies to the metal sites. The process drives electron transfer across the metal/oxide interface, affecting the nanoparticle charge, metal/support interaction, and overall chemical reactivity.

Atomic-scale imaging and spectroscopy have been applied to investigate solid/liquid interfaces [14, 15] but gaining direct atomic-level insight into the chemistry of these complex interfaces remains highly challenging at real-catalysis conditions of temperatures and pressures, which require going beyond standard UHV characterization tools. In addition, these interfacial effects are governed by a small number of atoms relative to the bulk phases, and their study requires experimental techniques with high interface sensitivity. In this context, *ab initio* molecular dynamics (AIMD) simulations have been shown to provide key atomic-level insight into interface dynamic processes of catalytic interfaces [16]. In particular, this method disclosed how the solvent alters elementary surface processes governing the catalytic properties of surface active sites, most notably the water dissociation equilibrium and dynamics at water/oxide interfaces [17,18]. While the examples studied so far focused mostly on short-range proton rearrangements, i.e. involving an interfacial water molecule and the closest surface site, the solvent can in principle assist also the long-range diffusion of adspecies [8,19], which is paramount for spillover effects in catalysis, and whose mechanisms and instances are far less understood.

We address this issue by employing AIMD simulations, focusing on the solvent-induced structural and electronic effects occurring at the interface between liquid water and the surface of ceria (CeO_2). Ceria is a highly reducible oxide, which has key applications in catalysis,[20] and which promotes the effective activation and dispersion of metal nanoparticles via strong metal-oxide electronic interactions [21, 22, 23]. XPS measurements and *ab-initio* static DFT calculations at $T=0\text{K}$ showed that water partially dissociates on the most stable $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ surface in UHV conditions [24, 25, 26-29]. Little is known on the atomistic structure and chemical processes of this interface in the presence of multilayer water at realistic reaction conditions, which is the subject of the present study.

COMPUTATIONAL METHODS:

The AIMD simulations were carried out in the framework of spin-polarized density functional theory, employing the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) [30] exchange-correlation functional and a Hubbard U term added to the Kohn-Sham energy functional (PBE+U). This well-

established method has been shown to be a reliable approach for ceria-based systems [10,31,32,33]. All the calculations employed periodic boundary conditions.

The interface between the stoichiometric $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ surface and water was modeled with periodic (4×4) supercell slabs consisting of two O-Ce-O trilayer separated, in the direction perpendicular to the surface, by more than 25 Å. This space was filled with 107 H_2O molecules providing a liquid-phase thickness of about 18 Å, while additional 7 Å of vacuum separated the water layer from the $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ periodic slab. The atoms in the lowest-laying O-Ce-O trilayer were constrained to their equilibrium bulk-like positions, while all the other atoms were free to move under the action of the interatomic forces. The results reported for this stoichiometric $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ surface in contact with water were obtained with Born Oppenheimer AIMD performed with the CP2K code [34]. The simulations parameters were chosen following previous studies on ceria surfaces [10,35]. The core electrons were described by scalar relativistic norm conserving pseudo potentials with 16 and 6 valence electrons for Ce and O, while the valence electrons were described with an auxiliary plane wave basis set with a cutoff of 500 Ry and using the Gamma point for Brillouin-zone integration. The Ce-4*f* occupancies entering the Hubbard U term were calculated on the basis of Mulliken population analysis, while the value of the parameter U was set to 7.0 eV, which was determined in previous works [10,35]. It is worth noting that there was no ceria reduction nor any change in the occupation of the Ce-4*f* states during these simulations and therefore the dynamics calculated with and without the inclusion of the Hubbard U term led to the same results. The canonical ensemble was employed with a target temperature of 350K using the “canonical sampling velocity rescaling” thermostat proposed by Bussi and coworkers [36] and a time step of 0.5 fs. The AIMD simulations generated ~ 30 ps of equilibrated trajectories. The hydrogen atoms were described as deuterium atoms.

The Pt/ CeO_2 /water system was modeled by a Pt_6 cluster supported on a stoichiometric $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ surface. The lowest-energy morphology of the supported cluster was determined in a previous work [37]. The CeO_2 substrate was modeled with (4×4) supercell slabs consisting of three O-Ce-O trilayer and separated by more than 15 Å in the direction perpendicular to the surface. The lowest-laying atoms in the O-Ce-O trilayer were constrained to their equilibrium bulk-like positions, while all other atoms were free to move under the action of the interatomic forces. The space between the periodic ceria slabs was filled with 66 H_2O molecules. The MD simulations for this Pt_6/CeO_2 system, as well as for reduced ceria surfaces, were performed with the Quantum-ESPRESSO package [46], and employed a plane-waves basis set and ultrasoft pseudopotentials. We used the PBE+U method as implemented by Cococcioni and de Gironcoli [38] and,

following our previous works, set the value of the parameter U to 4.5 eV [39-44]. The plane-wave energy cut off limiting the basis set used to describe the electronic wave function and density were set to 25 Ry and 250 Ry, respectively. Integrals in the Brillouin zone were performed at the Γ -point. The accuracy of these parameters in the MD simulations was determined and tested in our previous work (See SI in Ref. 45). The canonical ensemble was sampled with the Car-Parrinello propagation scheme, employing a fictitious orbital mass of 500 a.u. and a time step of 0.12 fs, for a total of ~ 30 ps of equilibrated trajectories. The target temperature of 350 K was controlled with a Nose-Hoover thermostat chain for ions and electrons. The hydrogen atoms were described as deuterium atoms. A second set of AIMD simulations (>30 ps) was run without the water layer so as to assess solvation effects..

RESULTS

Water dissociation and short-range proton transfer

In our density functional theory simulations, we initially focus on the interface between liquid water and the pure $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ surface (Fig. 1a). Starting from a slab of thermally-equilibrated liquid water having bulk structure (Fig. 1a), the interaction with the oxide surface drives the barrierless dissociation of a fraction of the interfacial water molecules and quickly leads to partial surface hydroxylation. A representative snapshot of the equilibrated interface structure resulting from the AIMD simulations is displayed in Fig. 1b. The analysis of the trajectories

shows that the dissociation of the interfacial water molecules proceeds via proton transfer to the closest surface O atoms. This leads to the formation of surface hydroxy groups and of solvated hydroxide ions (green and violet atoms in Fig. 1b), which increase the solvent density at the interface (Fig. 1c). One instance of this elementary reaction is displayed in Fig. 2a,b.

We analyze this proton transfer reaction in Fig. 2c, by plotting the time evolution of the interatomic distances between the surface O^{S} and water O_1 , H_1 atoms. The resulting hydroxide ion interacts with the surface Ce^{4+} sites more strongly than the neutral water molecules, hence hydroxides do not diffuse in the liquid bulk as they are confined at the interface by electrostatics. This increased interaction is reflected in the $\sim 15\%$ shortening of the $\langle \text{O}_1\text{-Ce} \rangle$ distance after dissociation (Fig. 2d). The spatial probability distribution function averaged over planes at 1 Å and 2.5 Å from the surface shows that, at equilibrium, the hydroxide ions reside indeed on the surface Ce^{4+} sites, while the remaining cation sites coordinate a solvent water molecule (Figs. 2e,f). This analysis also shows that the surface cation sublattice acts as a template for the water/hydroxide ad-species, transferring its symmetric atomic arrangement to the first surface solvation layer, which is therefore highly structured. As a result, the equilibrium water coverage at the oxide surface is close to 1 ML, and corresponds to a 60% increase of the water peak density at the solid/liquid interface, with a density peak of 1.65 g/cm^3 at $\sim 2 \text{ \AA}$ from the oxide surface (Fig. 1c).

Figure 1. Snapshots from the AIMD simulations of the model interface between water and the CeO₂(111) surface before (a) and after (b) partial dissociation of interfacial water. c) Planar average profile of the water density as a function of the distance from the CeO₂ surface. The origin of the distances in the water density profile is set to the average z coordinate of the surface O atoms.

Figure 2. Representative AIMD configurations showing the initial (a) and final (b) states of water dissociation leading to a surface hydroxyl group and to a solvated hydroxide. c,d) Time evolution of representative interatomic distances (denoted by “< >” symbols) during water dissociation. Surface O atoms are labeled by O^S, O₁ and H₁ refer to the O and H atoms involved in a specific water dissociation, while O_i indicates other water O atoms. Spatial probability distribution function of O and H atoms averaged over planes at 1 Å (e) and 2.5 Å (f) from the CeO₂ surface. Number of adsorbed H⁺/OH⁻ as a function of time (g). Light green, dark red, purple and gray areas represent the distribution of the protons, water O atoms, hydroxide O atoms, and water/hydroxide H atoms, respectively.

The statistics of water dissociation accumulated during the simulations (Fig. 2g) show that equilibrium is reached after ~15 ps, in which an average of ~20% of the surface

O sites (denoted as O^S) are hydroxylated. As a result, Ce-O^SH⁺, Ce-OH⁻ and Ce-OH₂ sites coexist on the solvated surface, which therefore displays amphoteric behavior [46b]. Similarly to what reported for other oxide surfaces

[9, 10, 11], after this transient, the dissociation of water molecules in the first surface solvation layer becomes a reversible dynamic process, which is governed by solvent-induced short-ranged transfers of protons between adsorbed water (Ce-OH_2) and the surface O^{S} sites, or, in the reverse process, between surface hydroxy groups ($\text{Ce-O}^{\text{S}}\text{H}^+$) and hydroxide ions (Ce-OH^-). Our results demonstrate that the solvent-induced proton hopping identified by Tocci and Michaelides for the $\text{ZnO}(10\bar{1}0)$ non-reducible surface [9] is also active at the $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ highly-reducible surface.

We remark that during all the MD simulations reported above, the water interaction and dissociation at the stoichiometric $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ surface does not induce substrate reduction, i. e. all the Ce ions preserve their 4+ oxidation state (Supplementary Fig. 7). Instead, repeating the simulations starting from a reduced ceria surface, i.e. including an O vacancy and the related 2 Ce^{3+} ions in the ceria slab, we observe that one interfacial water molecule quickly (~ 70 fs) dissociates at the O vacancy, leading to the formation of 2 surface hydroxy $\text{Ce-O}^{\text{S}}\text{H}^+$ groups (Supplementary Fig. 8) and 2 substrate Ce^{3+} ions, in full analogy to the vacuum case [27,28,29].

Figure 3. Representative AIMD configurations showing the initial (a) and final (b) states of the proton chain leading to long-range hydroxide diffusion at the ceria/water interface. c,d,e) Time evolution of representative interatomic distances (denoted by “ $\langle \rangle$ ”) and collective variables during hydroxide diffusion. See text and figure 4d for definition of λ .

Hydroxide dynamics and long-range proton transfer

Besides the short-range proton transfer, the analysis of the AIMD trajectories reveals the existence of another diffusion process active at the water/oxide interface. This is a longer ranged proton transfer that determines the diffusion of protons and hydroxide ions along the solid-liquid interface (Fig. 3), effectively leading to hydroxide hopping between surface sites separated by more than 3.5 Å. To analyze this more complex process, we introduce two collective variables (CVs): $d_{i,j} = \langle O_i - O_j \rangle$ and $\lambda_{i,j} = \langle O_i - H_i \rangle - \langle O_j - H_i \rangle$, where i and j label water or

hydroxide molecules in the simulation cell [46c]. The time-evolution of some of these CVs during three representative proton-transfer events are displayed in Fig. 3, while their physical meaning is graphically represented in Fig. 4e. $d_{i,j}$ is the distance between the two O atoms of water/hydroxide molecules labeled by i and j (see black dashed lines in Fig. 4e). $\lambda_{i,j}$ describes the position of a proton with respect to the O atoms of the two water molecules i and j (red dotted lines in Fig. 4e): when $\lambda_{i,j} > 0$ the proton is bound to O_j , while when $\lambda_{i,j} < 0$ the proton is bound to O_i .

By analyzing the trajectories with these collective variables, we identify two active mechanisms for interface hydroxide diffusion: i) A direct proton transfer between an adsorbed water molecule and a neighboring hydroxide ion (Fig. 3c), and ii) proton transfer chains mediated by solvent water molecules, which bridge between surface hydroxide and surface water molecules (stepwise, Fig. 3d, or concerted, Fig. 3e). In the latter case, the mechanism involves two proton transfers: One proton from the assisting water molecule (H_2 in Fig. 3) to the hydroxide (O_3-H), hence transforming it into interfacial water molecule. The other proton transfers from the adsorbed (H_1) to the assisting water molecule, hence transforming the former into a surface hydroxide. The overall effect of this diffusion process, which is reminiscent of the Grotthus mechanism between Zundel and Eigen complexes in bulk water [47], is to transfer hydroxide ions selectively along the water/oxide interface between different surface sites.

Thermodynamics and kinetics

We calculate the free energy ΔG controlling these short- and long-range proton transfers at $T=350K$ by applying the formula $\Delta G = -k_B T \log P$, where k_B is the Boltzmann constant and P is the probability distribution function defined in terms of CVs capturing the different diffusion mechanisms. For the long range process, the probability function P is obtained from the AIMD trajectories by accumulating the population histograms of the $d_{i,j}$ and $\lambda_{i,j}$ variables introduced above:

$$P(d, \lambda) = \int_0^\infty \sum_{i \neq j} \delta(d - d_{i,j}(t)) \delta(\lambda - \lambda_{i,j}(t)) dt,$$

where δ is the Dirac function. The probability function for the short-range process P^S is obtained with an equivalent methodology employing the modified collective variables $d_{i,j}^S = \langle O_i - O_j^S \rangle$, and $\lambda_{i,j}^S = \langle O_i - H_i \rangle - \langle O_j^S - H_i \rangle$, where the index i labels the water/hydroxide molecules, while j labels the surface oxygen atoms, O^S (Fig. 4e). $d_{i,j}$ is the distance between a surface O^S atom and a water O atom, labeled by j and i , respectively. It therefore captures whether surface proximity of the water molecule is relevant for its dissociation and for proton transfer to the surface. $\lambda_{i,j}^S$ describes the position of the proton, whether bound to the surface ($\lambda_{i,j}^S > 0$) or to a water molecule ($\lambda_{i,j}^S < 0$). The resulting free energy maps are displayed in Fig. 4, while the corresponding probability distribution functions (P, P^S) are reported in the Supplementary Fig. 1. Fig. 4 plots the free energy differences for the short- and long-range proton transfers, ΔG^S and ΔG respectively, calculated in the 2-dimensional subspace spanned by the corresponding CVs. The green areas in Fig. 4a represent the distinct free energy basins in which a proton is bound to the surface (O^S-H state, right) or to a water molecule ($H-O-H$ state, left). The free energy map is

asymmetric because the two minima refer to chemically different configurations, which therefore undergo different equilibrium dynamics. In particular, the system in the O^S-H surface state explores a larger range of interatomic distances. Consequently, the forward and backwards reactions are also different, being related to water dissociation or formation. From this analysis we estimate the activation energy for the short-range proton diffusion to be ~ 0.1 eV, which is in line the values calculated by Tocci and Michaelides for the same process on wet ZnO surfaces [9].

Figure 4. Calculated free energy maps for the short-range proton transfer (a) and long-range hydroxide diffusion (b) as a function of the corresponding collective variables defined in panels (c) and (d). (e) Scheme indicating the interatomic distances entering the definition of d^S and d (see black dashed lines), and of λ^S and λ (see red dotted lines).

The free energy map for the long-range proton transfer is displayed in Fig. 4b. It is obviously symmetric because the two minima refer to chemically equivalent configurations and because the interface is homogeneous and there is no preferential surface site for the hydroxide adsorption. Therefore, the forward and backward reactions are equivalent. The calculated activation energy for this process (0.07 eV) is as small as that one for interfacial water dissociation. It is evident from the free energy maps in Fig. 5 that water dissociation and proton diffusion are correlated with the shortening of O-O distances (d^S and d CVs). The increased water density at the ceria/water interface shortens the O-O distance and therefore promotes the fast and interface diffusion processes.

Relevance for wet catalysis: Ceria-supported Pt clusters

The small activation energy for long-range hydroxide diffusion along the water/ceria interface indicates that this

process could participate in the wet heterogeneous catalysis of ceria-based materials at room temperature. To demonstrate this, we focus on a Pt_6 nanoparticle supported by the $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ surface. Ceria-supported Pt nanoparticles are key catalysts in fuel production and purification, environmental chemistry and chemical industry [20]. To assess the relevance of the long-range proton transfer on the catalysis of supported Pt nanoparticles, we consider the $\text{Pt}_6/\text{CeO}_2(111)$ model system, which we have fully characterized in the gas phase [32]. By comparing the simulations of the Pt/CeO2 surface in vacuum and in solution, we can anticipate that the solvent increases the charge transfer from the cluster to the ceria support by ~ 1 -2 electrons, so that, on average, the charge of the cluster decreases upon solvation. However it turns out that the solvation effects on the electronic properties of the catalyst and on the charge state of the supported nanoparticle

are complex and dependent on many factors, including the adsorption and dissociation sites of the water molecules, the relative distance between the dissociated H and OH products adsorbed on the catalyst, the dynamic evolution of the cluster structure, and others. Due to this complexity, a complete analysis of these effects will be reported elsewhere [48]. We focus here primarily on the catalytic effects of proton diffusion at (Pt)ceria/water interface. In particular, we show specific instances in which the interface diffusion mechanisms described above participate into the water dissociation catalyzed by the Pt nanoparticles, accelerating the direct spillover of the H/OH species over distances larger than 4.9 Å. Three snapshots from the AIMD simulation representing this event occurring during the AIMD simulation run are displayed in Fig. 5a-c.

Figure 5. Snapshots from the AIMD simulations showing the initial (a), intermediate (b), and final (c) configurations for water dissociation at the periphery of a Pt_6 cluster supported by the CeO_2 surface. d) Analysis of the reaction in terms of the $\langle \text{Pt-O} \rangle$ distance (dashed line) and of the charge difference (Bader) calculated for the Pt_6 cluster, H_2O molecules and CeO_2 slab (solid lines). Negative/positive values of Δq indicate electron increase/decrease. The inset in panel d) reports the charge difference analysis for water dissociation in vacuum.

A water molecule of the solvation layer dissociates at the periphery of the supported nanoparticle into a

hydroxide ion and a proton. This activates the dissociation of a neighboring solvent water molecule (see ovals in Fig. 5a,b), which mediates the fast proton chains at the

water/oxide interface described before and effectively transfers the proton at an oxide surface site 4.9 Å away from the nanoparticle, forming a surface hydroxyl (Fig. 5c). The resulting OH⁻ species readily binds to a Pt site of the supported cluster where it drives substantial charge transfer across the metal/oxide interface.

The electron reorganization of the Pt/CeO₂ nanocatalyst is analyzed in Fig. 5d in terms of Bader charge differences (Δq) calculated for the Pt₆, water, and CeO₂ slabs (solid lines), and of the Pt-OH distance (dashed line). This plot reveals two concomitant charge transfers driven by water dissociation at the solvated Pt/ceria interface (see the region between the vertical lines): i) The cluster transfers one electron to the ceria substrate (black line), and ii) the hydroxide ion binds to the Pt cluster and releases one electron, thus turning into a neutral OH adsorbate (blue line). Quite surprisingly, the latter electron is also transferred to the ceria substrate. Overall, about two electrons, one from the hydroxide species and one from the cluster, are transferred from the OH-Pt₆ system to the oxide substrate through the metal/oxide interface (red line), thus demonstrating that the cluster/solvent and metal/oxide interfaces are strongly coupled. The reason of this effect stems from the high reducibility of the substrate, which can accommodate the excess electrons on the Ce-*f* states by the easy Ce⁴⁺ → Ce³⁺ oxidation changes. Our vacuum simulations for water dissociation at the Pt₆/CeO₂ catalysis never showed the two-electron charge transfer reported above for the solvated catalyst. The charge analysis of the initial and final states of water dissociation is displayed in the inset of Fig. 5d. It shows that the vacuum reaction environment reduces the charge transfer by a factor of ~2. Most importantly, in vacuum, the charge transferred involves only the hydroxide adsorbate and the ceria surface, while the cluster charge remains unaffected.

We note that, given the concerted reaction mechanism, the process described above cannot be distinguished from the one in which a water molecule dissociate at a ceria surface site far from the cluster and the hydroxide ion is then transferred to the Pt nanoparticle by the proton-chain in the solvent (Fig. 5 c,b,a sequence). In both cases, the supported Pt clusters acts as a basin of attraction for the hydroxide products, which therefore will accumulate at the cluster sites.

DISCUSSION

The molecular and dissociative adsorption of water on CeO₂(111) in vacuum conditions and at T=0 K were reported to be almost isoenergetic and to be separated by a small energy barrier (<0.2 eV) [26,29]. Quite consistently, our simulations demonstrate that room temperature wet reaction conditions drive the spontaneous dissociation of a fraction of the interfacial water molecules. The dissociated state is further stabilized by hydroxide solvation and electrostatic screening by the solvent. The

spontaneous dissociation of interfacial water molecules indicates that the O sites of the clean CeO₂(111) surface act as Brønsted bases. The resulting partial hydroxylation of the solvated ceria surface generates two interface-specific sites, Ce-OH₂ and Ce-OH⁻, that form a conjugate pair and that govern the proton hopping along the ceria/water interface reported above. In this framework, the proton chains leading to the hydroxyl diffusion proceed between the Ce-OH₂ and Ce-OH⁻ sites, which act as Brønsted acid and base, respectively. The water-ceria interface therefore has a clear amphoteric behavior, in line with other oxides such as SiO₂, TiO₂ or ZrO₂ [8, 49,50]. Similar conjugate pairs involving sites of the oxide and of the supported Pt nanoparticle determine the accelerated spillover of ad-species between the metal and oxide sites during wet catalysis. On the basis of these results we cannot address the issue of competitive adsorption on solvated surface catalysts. In the context of Mars and Van Krevelen mechanisms at oxide-supported metal catalysts, the proton transfer at the metal-support interface has been shown to be a key reaction step in several reactions, promoting the binding and selected activation of adsorbed intermediates [56,57]. M15: The amphoteric nature of the Pt/CeO₂ surface certainly plays an important role in these cases: The same basic sites that accept a proton and form solvated hydroxy species can in a later stage become acid sites and transfer the proton to the supported metal, thus participating into complex catalytic reactions.

The point of zero net proton charge (PZC) measured for ceria systems are typically above 7: In particular, Trasatti and coworkers reported a PZC value of 8.1 for several commercial samples [51,52]. The present calculations are a valuable starting point for a theoretical prediction of the PZC, however its reliable calculation requires more specific approaches capable to address the acidities of the related surface groups, such as those developed and applied for TiO₂ or SiO₂ surfaces [49,50]. In this context, we note that, by construction, our simulations sample the PZC surface condition, since the concentrations of the surface Ce-OH⁺ hydroxy and the Ce-OH⁻ hydroxylates turn out to be equal, both of them resulting from the dissociation of neutral water molecules.

Our results for the solvated Pt/CeO₂ system demonstrate how solvation of oxide-supported metal nanocatalysts can strongly modify the electronic structure of the catalyst, affecting the metal-support interaction, which is central for the increased catalytic activity displayed by metal clusters supported on reducible oxides [21, 22, 23]. In particular, it is well established that the higher activity of Pt/ceria catalysts as compared to pure Pt systems stems from the O-storage capacity and high reducibility of the ceria support [20], which activate the supported Pt particles via electron transfer at the metal/oxide interface and via strong metal-support interaction. To date, the majority

of the theoretical studies addressing the interaction between ceria and water were static calculations performed at $T = 0$ K and focused on the adsorption of a single or few water molecules on clean or reduced CeO_2 surfaces [26, 27, 28, 29]. Previous AIMD simulations of ceria surfaces in vacuum conditions indeed established the importance of dynamic processes at ceria-based catalytic surfaces [10,41]. The present results demonstrate how the rich dynamics of the solid/liquid interface impact on the metal-support interaction and hence on the catalytic properties of oxide-supported metal nanoparticles in wet conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

Our simulations show that, upon solvation, surfaces of ceria-based materials can become proton conductors. Similar conclusions were reported for bohemite surface steps and for hydrated zirconia (ZrO_2) surfaces [19,8]. Indeed, high conductivity has been measured for nanostructured ceria and zirconia materials in humidified atmosphere [53]. It was proposed that the origin of this high conductivity is related to the presence of water layers trapped between the grain boundaries of the polycrystalline materials [54]. The present theoretical results provide atomic-level support to the low-T proton conductivity of ceria-based systems and therefore underpin their possible application as electrolytes in fuel cells [55]. More generally, the accelerated spillover between metal and oxide sites, together with its impact on the metal-support interaction, opens new perspectives in wet heterogeneous catalysis by oxide-supported metal nanoparticles.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information.

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website.

This file includes:

Supplementary Note 1: Probability distributions and free energies

Supplementary Figures 1 to 3;

Supplementary Note 2: Validation of computational parameters

Supplementary Figures 4 and 5;

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